

SEASONAL DEVELOPMENTAL DYNAMICS OF AERVA LANATA BASED ON 2022–2024 OBSERVATIONS

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of a study on the seasonal developmental stages of Aerva lanata under the environmental conditions of the Kashkadarya region during the period of 2022–2024. Based on phenological observations, the effects of climatic factors such as temperature, humidity and other environmental conditions on the plant's growth and development during the vegetation period were analyzed. The findings provide insights into the adaptability of Aerva lanata to introduction conditions and serve as a basis for evaluating its agrobiological characteristics.*

Keywords: *Aerva lanata L., phenology, vegetation period, introduction, generative phases, climatic factors.*

Introduction

The study of seasonal developmental dynamics is of significant importance in the development of introduction strategies and cultivation technologies for medicinal plants. Based on phenological observations, the plant's response to climatic factors, duration of developmental phases, productivity potential, and changes in ontogenetic stages can be determined.

The research was conducted from 2022 to 2024 in experimental fields located in the Shakhrisabz and Muborak districts of the Kashkadarya region. The sowing schemes used were 70×20 cm and 70×30 cm. The phenological stages—seed germination, true leaf formation, stem development, budding, flowering, and fruiting—were recorded according to the calendar timeline. Aerometeorological data, including daily temperature and relative humidity, were taken into account during the study period.

During the years 2022–2024, the germination period of seeds lasted between 10 to 12 days, and variations in temperature and relative humidity had a notable impact on this phase. For example, in 2024, seeds sown on March 4th germinated by March 15th under conditions of 16°C temperature and 47% relative humidity. Under these conditions, germination occurred rapidly and uniformly. Within 8 to 12 days after the appearance of cotyledon leaves, true leaves developed, reaching a height of 1.5 to 3 cm. During this stage, lignification at the root collar was also observed. In April, with air temperatures ranging between 22–25°C, stem elongation and branch development accelerated. Throughout the 2022–2024 observation period, both primary and secondary lateral branches formed, with 15 to 20 branches developing on a single plant. In 2022, the maximum plant height was recorded at 91.7 cm, indicating the peak of vegetative growth.

Budding began between days 60–65 after sowing, and flowering occurred between days 65–70. The number of flowers per plant ranged from approximately 45,000 to 65,000. The flowering period lasted between 32 to 70 days. The flowers were small, reddish-pink in color, bisexual, and exhibited irregular symmetry.

The fruiting phase began in early July and continued for 12–25 days. Fruit ripening started in the second half of September and lasted for 30–35 days. Vegetation ended in late October to early November, with a total vegetation period ranging from 218 to 243 days.

The research demonstrated that *Aerva lanata* adapts well to the environmental conditions of the Kashkadarya region. Despite differences in temperature and humidity across the years, the plant consistently completed all seasonal developmental stages. Biometric indicators such as vegetation duration, timing of generative phases, and stem growth serve as a foundation for the cultivation of *Aerva lanata* in agricultural settings. These findings are essential for developing appropriate agrotechnical practices.

Dividing and studying the seasonal developmental stages of a plant plays an important role in the assessment of its introduction potential and in developing cultivation strategies. It allows researchers to determine the plant's resistance, productivity, duration and timing of vital physiological processes, and also contributes to its successful domestication. The seasonal growth patterns of plants reflect their adaptation to ecological, coenotic, and climatic conditions of the surrounding environment.

To fully understand the seasonal development patterns of plants within various phytocenoses, it is essential to study not only the formation of individual shoots but also the entire plant body. This approach helps reveal how plants adapt to natural conditions and how they exhibit growth tendencies under changing environmental circumstances [71; p. 506].

The seasonal development of *Aerva lanata* was studied based on observations carried out during 2022–2024 under experimental conditions. Key elements of phenological observation—such as seed germination, formation of true leaves, development of assimilating leaves, stem branching and shaping, budding, flowering, and fruiting—were recorded throughout the vegetation period, allowing for the acquisition of scientifically significant results.

In the 2022 field experiments, seeds sown in the second decade of March (10.03.2022) began germinating on March 21—11 days after sowing—which marked the beginning of the vegetation period. At that time, the air temperature was recorded at 22°C, with a relative humidity of 41%. Mass seed germination was observed 25 days after sowing, on April 4, with an air temperature of 23.2°C and relative humidity around 31%.

In 2023, seeds sown on March 10 germinated on March 21, 12 days later, when the temperature was 19°C and relative humidity was about 37%. Mass germination occurred around March 26, with the temperature at 22°C and relative humidity recorded at 48%. In 2024, seeds were sown earlier on March 4, and germinated by March 15. At that time, the air temperature was 16°C and relative humidity was 47%. Mass emergence was recorded on March 20, with an average temperature of 18°C and relative humidity around 62%.

The experiments indicate that the rapid development of the aerial parts of the plant is directly influenced by climatic and soil conditions. In 2022, the transition from seedling to juvenile stage took 10 days. In 2023, this phase was longer, taking 18 days—mainly due to a temperature drop to 5–7°C between March 21 and 26. In the 2024 trials, this transition period lasted 12 days. The active growth of above-ground organs occurred predominantly during April and May in all three years (2022–2024). Furthermore, studies on *Aerva lanata* L. conducted using both seed-based and seedling-based planting methods throughout 2022–2024 were analyzed, and a detailed phenospectrum of the plant was constructed (see Appendices 2–3).

In field experiments conducted under the typical grey soil conditions of the Shakhrisabz district, *Aerva lanata* was introduced by direct seeding using two planting schemes (70×20 cm and

70×30 cm). In the first growing season (sowing date: 10.03.2022), the average seed germination rate was recorded at $53.65 \pm 1.02\%$. The flowering phase of the generative period began between days 60–65 after sowing. Under different conditions (e.g., in Muborak district), this stage showed a variability of 8–12 days, which gradually decreased by the end of the budding stage.

Seed germination occurred within 10–12 days, producing cotyledons measuring 3–5 mm in length and 1–2 mm in width. By day 15 of development, the seedlings reached an average height of 1.5–3 cm, typically bearing one true leaf. The true leaf was measured at 1.2 ± 0.04 cm in length and 0.32 ± 0.03 cm in width, while the plant's average diameter was 0.140 ± 0.006 cm, covered with fine soft hairs. Cotyledons remained attached, ranging from 0.5–0.7 cm in length and 0.4–0.6 cm in width. At this stage, the stem base exhibited a color transition from dark green to reddish-brown, with lignification starting at a diameter of 0.2 cm.

The development of true leaves continued until the end of August. By then, the average true leaf length reached 3.2 cm, and the average width was 2.2 cm.

Development of Seeds and Leaves of Aerva lanata L.

True leaves began to emerge 8–12 days after the appearance of the cotyledons. For instance, by March 28, some seedlings had already produced their first true leaves, while others developed them between April 6 and 10. The root system of the plant is strongly developed, forming multiple roots. The primary root reaches a length of up to 4.2 ± 0.06 cm, with the formation of numerous lateral roots.

The stems of *Aerva lanata* are dark green in color and covered with fine hairs. The plant develops both simple and compound leaves, which are initially arranged oppositely on the stem and later alternate. The leaves are lanceolate-ovate or ovate-elliptical in shape. The lower leaves are relatively larger and gradually become smaller toward the upper parts of the stem.

Approximately **30–35 days** after sowing, the stem height reached **10–12 cm**, and the formation of lateral stems was observed. These lateral stems were thinner and more delicate

compared to the main stem. Branching typically started from the lower nodes of the main stem, forming first- and second-order lateral stems.

The first- and second-order stems predominantly developed in the basal regions of the plant, with their numbers ranging between **15 to 20** per plant. These stems developed rapidly and eventually reached or exceeded the height of the main stem. Additionally, the plant continued forming new stems, which were relatively smaller and contributed to the formation of supplementary leaf biomass. However, the number and mass of leaves formed on these smaller stems were significantly lower compared to those on the main stem, both in quantity and size.

In the 2022 trials, *Aerva lanata* plants entered the immature stage at 50–54 days of vegetation, while in 2023 this occurred later, at 56–68 days, indicating a comparatively longer developmental period. A delay of 4–5 days was also observed in the transition to the generative phase in 2023 compared to 2022. However, the fruiting period remained relatively consistent across all years, lasting between 12 and 25 days. Similarly, the fruit ripening duration showed little variation from year to year.

Approximately 60–65 days after sowing, the first signs of budding were observed. In a single model plant, an average of 1,300–1,500 buds were formed—200–300 on the main stem and 80–120 on lateral branches. In total, 45,000 to 65,000 flowers were produced per plant. Flowering began around days 65–68, and the interval between budding and full flowering was approximately 3–5 days. The inflorescences formed in the axils of leaves, were spike-like, and the flowers were small, reddish-pink, bisexual, and zygomorphic, with a bell-shaped calyx during blooming.

Literature sources [36; pp. 46–50] report stem height for *Aerva lanata* to range from 60 to 80 cm. However, under the conditions of the Qashqadaryo oasis during 2022–2024, stem height varied significantly—from a minimum of 22 cm to a maximum of 91 cm, with the tallest stems observed in 2022. The average height recorded in that year was 91.7 cm. On the main stem, 8–18 first-order, 8–24 second-order, and 5–11 third-order lateral branches were recorded. The total number of leaves ranged from 340 to 450, and the average number of flowers per plant was around 55,000.

During the vegetation period, the seeds of *Aerva lanata* initially appear brown and later turn black upon full maturation. The seeds are kidney-shaped. The average length of the pedicels or fruit stalks is between 0.25–0.3 cm. The spike-shaped inflorescences are arranged sequentially in the leaf axils, and each spike typically contains 35 to 40 flowers. The seasonal developmental phases of *Aerva lanata* showed relatively similar trends depending on climatic conditions. A comparative analysis of the plant's growth in both study locations indicated that the seasonal growth stages largely depended on air temperature.

For example:

- In 2022, the budding stage lasted 5 days, flowering 6 days, and the fruiting stage extended for 52 days.
- In 2023, budding lasted 3 days, flowering 8 days, and fruiting 49 days.
- In 2024, budding extended to 7 days, flowering to 11 days, and fruiting lasted up to 54 days.

These findings emphasize that the plant's phenological timing is primarily influenced by ambient temperature conditions. The fruit ripening process of *Aerva lanata* primarily begins in the second half of autumn, especially during the second decade of September, and lasts approximately 30–35 days. Leaf yellowing is first visibly observed in the lower parts of the plant around

September 13–19, 2022, when average air temperatures reached 39–40°C and relative humidity ranged between 18–22%.

The end of the vegetation period is marked by the wilting, yellowing, and drying of the lower leaves. As this process continues, the upper parts of the plant, particularly the generative organs, begin to turn reddish and dry out, eventually leading to seed dispersal. The final stage of vegetation concludes with the complete drying of the above-ground biomass. Vegetation termination occurred in late October to early November, with a total growth cycle duration ranging between 218 to 243 days:

- In 2022: 238 days
- In 2023: 231 days
- In 2024: 233 days

Research confirms that seasonal developmental variations in *Aerva lanata* are strongly influenced by local climatic and soil conditions in the Qashqadaryo region. Rising air temperatures to 20–25°C during late spring (May) significantly accelerate vegetative growth. Conversely, a drop in temperature may delay development or even cause premature seed drop before reaching full maturity. The onset of flowering was associated with increased temperatures of 30–35°C or higher, and relative humidity levels between 45–52%, or occasionally lower.

Throughout the vegetation cycle:

- The budding phase lasted 20–28 days
- The flowering phase spanned 32–70 days
- The fruiting phase continued for 12–20 days

In general, the total vegetation period of *Aerva lanata* was found to last 218–243 days, depending on the year and environmental conditions. The differences between the native habitat of *Aerva lanata* and the environmental conditions of the Qashqadaryo oasis—particularly in terms of climate and soil—explain the slight shifts observed in its ontogenetic stages, particularly flowering and fruiting. Despite these differences, the plant successfully completed all phases of its ontogeny under the studied introduction conditions.

A sharp drop in air temperature during the early vegetation period (March) did not cause damage to young seedlings, although it led to an extended seedling stage. Based on the observed data, this phenomenon may be attributed to the species' evolutionary adaptation traits—namely, its inherent tolerance to low temperatures.

Seasonal Developmental Stages of Aerva lanata (2022–2024)

№	Phenological Stage	2022 year	2023 year	2024 year
1	Seed germination	21 March	21 March	15 March
2	Full emergence	4 April	26 March	20 March
3	Emergence of true leaves	28 March – 10 April	30 March – 8 April	27 March – 5 April
4	Transition from seedling to juvenile stage	1–10 April	8–18 April	3–15 April
5	Intensive growth (stem elongation)	15–30 April	20 April – 5 May	18 April – 3 May
6	Onset of branching	10 April – 5 May	15 April – 7 May	12 April – 4 May

№	Phenological Stage	2022 year	2023 year	2024 year
7	End of branching	5 - 12 July	7 – 21 July	4 – 18 July
8	Beginning of budding	10 May	12 May	14 May
9	Beginning of flowering	15 May	18 May	20 May
10	Beginning of fruiting	6 July – 28 July	7 July – 25 July	8 July – 30 July
11	Fruit ripening period	15 September – 20 October	16 September – 18 October	18 September – 22 October
12	Leaf yellowing	13–19 September	14–18 September	15–19 September
13	End of vegetation	3 November	1 November	2 November

Conclusion

The conducted research demonstrated that *Aerva lanata* exhibits strong adaptability to the environmental conditions of the Qashqadaryo region. Despite variations in temperature and humidity across different years, the plant successfully completed all stages of its seasonal development. Biometric indicators such as vegetation duration, the length of generative phases, and stem development confirm the species' suitability for cultivation. These findings are essential for developing effective agro-technical practices for the successful domestication and large-scale cultivation of *Aerva lanata*.

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